

COMPUTER SELF-EFFICACY, BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS AND USE OF ONLINE INFORMATION RESOURCES BY LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE STUDENTS IN KWARA STATE

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Abstract

In the contemporary landscape of information dissemination, the use of online resources has become increasingly integral to academic and professional pursuits. However, the proliferation of online information resources that should have been a blessing, has posed a serious challenge to students, in terms of retrieval and usage. Therefore, this study examined computer self-efficacy, behavioural skills, and use of online information resources among Library and Information Science (LIS) students in Kwara State. There were 8 universities in Kwara State, out of which 3 were selected for the study. The selected universities are: University of Ilorin, Kwara State University and Al-Hikma University, Ilorin. A total of 523 final year LIS students of the three universities constituted the population. Using a Random Number Generator from within the range of 100 to 120 while allowing for duplicate numbers, a sample size of 108 was drawn. Questionnaire was used as data collection instrument. Its internal consistency strength was tested, and it yielded

a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.71, indicating an acceptable level of reliability. One hundred and eight structured and validated copies of the questionnaire were administered, and only 88 were returned, giving the return rate of 81.5%. The returned copies were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 24). Frequency distribution, percentage and arithmetic mean were used to present data. Findings revealed an indication of a low level of computer self-efficacy among the LIS students. Students exhibited behavioural skills for using search engines to find scholarly information. This reliance on search engines seemed to explain why students used online resources provided by their libraries very less often. The study concluded that students' poor disposition towards the use of OIRs of library is partly attributable to the challenges posed by complex nature of the advanced search features of the online library databases. Therefore, the University management should hold regular training sessions and integrate digital literacy courses into the curriculum to enhance computer self-efficacy of students in order to maximally explore the under used OIRs.

Keywords: Computer self-efficacy, Behavioural skills, Online information resources, LIS students

Introduction

Since the turn of the 21st century, there has been an exponential increase in the number of online resources introduced by libraries. E-resources such as e-journals, e-books, e-theses, and e-databases are growing exponentially. Most libraries have leveraged on the emerging technologies to make OIRs available to students. There is now a paradigm shift from paper-based information to online resources. However, availability of these resources does not translate to accessibility. Resources may be available but not accessible to the students. On the other

hand, accessibility does not also translate to usability. These OIRs are only useful when they are fully explored by the students.

Full exploration of OIRs is reliant on students' computer self-efficacy and behavioural skills. Computer self-efficacy as a concept has root in Bandura's theory (1997) and it highlights individuals' beliefs in their competences to effectively use computer technologies to complete tasks. Students need to be confident in their ability to use Information technology and also demonstrate some moral and ethical skills. These skills are very crucial to retrieving and utilising

relevant OIRs, given the current reality of information explosion. Computer self-efficacy is critical for molding students' attitudes towards technology adoption and engagement with online learning resources. Students must exhibit competence in the use of technology for them to access and use OIRs (Lent & Lopez 2016; Cheng & Yeh 2015).

Complementing the concept of computer self-efficacy are the behavioural skills required for efficient information seeking, evaluation, and use. In the ever-changing field of Library and Information Science (LIS) education, behavioural skills encompass a spectrum of competences, including critical thinking. The convergence of digital technologies, behavioural skills and OIRs has become a central focus of academic research and professional practice. This underscores the need for skills by LIS students to make adequate use of online resources to locate discrete knowledge items and if the competence is not there to enable them navigate the Internet for OIRs, their academic and research needs may suffer a setback (Akpojotor, 2016).

Martzoukou (2021) has stressed the important role of academic librarians in helping students to develop information,

digital and media literacy skills so that they can select, access and use accurate, reliable and credible sources of information on their own, for both their academic studies and personal well-being. However, students' access to e-resources has been limited due to inadequate telecommunications

infrastructure, poor user skills in navigating e-resources, and the high cost of Internet subscriptions. These factors have created significant obstacles to LIS students' use of OIRs in Nigerian universities (Akpojotor, 2016; Oshinaike, 2021; Uukongo, 2023; Mogaka, 2024). In this regard, investigating the three key variables, namely computer self-efficacy, behavioural skills, and the use of OIRs will provide useful insights that could enhance the learning experiences and information practices of LIS students.

Statement of the Problem

In the contemporary landscape of information dissemination, the utilization of online resources has become increasingly integral to academic and professional pursuits. Within the domain of library and information science education, understanding the factors that influence students' effective engagement with OIRs is imperative. Preliminary investigations revealed that proliferation of online

information resource that should have been a blessing, is now posing a serious challenge to LIS students, in terms of retrieval and usage. There is a notable gap in scholarly exploration regarding the topic around students' level of computer self-efficacy, behavioural skills, and the use of OIRs. Lack of computer self-efficacy and inability to demonstrate good behavioural skills by the

students of LIS affect their full exploration of online information materials, and consequently they were found lagging behind in fully exploiting OIRs for their academic pursuits. Therefore, this study examined computer self-efficacy, behavioural skills, and the use of OIRs among LIS students in Kwara State.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study was to investigate the computer self-efficacy, behavioural skills and effective use of OIRs by LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara state. The following specific questions guided the study:

1. What is the level of computer self-efficacy among LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara state?
2. What behavioural skills do LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara state exhibit when accessing OIRs?
3. To what extent do LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara state use OIRs for academic and professional purposes?
4. What attitudinal disposition do LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara state exhibited when using OIRs?

Review of Related Literature

Computer self-efficacy is the perceived capability of students to effectively use and navigate computer system and other information technologies to access, retrieve and use OIRs in the course of their academic pursuits. There is a significant improvement

in the use of OIRs when students are equipped with basic computer literacy skills. It will aid their information retrieval ability (Alexander & Zhu, 2018). Similarly, Wang and We (2019) corroborated this by asserting that computer self-efficacy instils confidence in students' ability to explore relevant OIRs.

Computer self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to effectively use computers and related technology. This concept is part of Bandura's broader theory of self-efficacy, which suggests that a person's confidence in their abilities can significantly influence their performance and motivation. High computer self-efficacy can lead to greater engagement with technology, increase willingness to learn new skills, and improve problem-solving when faced with tech-related challenges. Conversely, low computer self-efficacy may result in avoidance of technology or feelings of frustration when using it. Computer self-efficacy is crucial in shaping the attitudes, behaviours, and outcomes of LIS students in an increasingly digital world.

On the other hand, behavioural skill is a twin brother of computer self-efficacy in the effective use of OIRs. Apart from information technology skills, the way students interact with online environment with respect to moral and ethics could also determine the usage of OIRs. Behavioural skill encompasses traits like adaptability, emotional regulation, social skills, and problem-solving abilities. Essentially, it's about how effectively a person can behave in

ways that are appropriate and effective in different contexts, such as in social interactions or during challenges.

Inability of LIS students to demonstrate computer self-efficacy and good behavioural skills constitute a whole lot of challenges in their exploration of OIRs. The challenges range from technological limitations, information overload, and digital literacy gaps. Technological challenges include difficulties in navigating complex online databases and platforms, as well as inadequate access to high-speed Internet and digital devices, particularly in under-resourced settings. Information overload poses a significant hurdle, as students struggle to filter and evaluate the vast amount of online information available, leading to confusion and inefficiency in information retrieval processes (Rao, 2024). Moreover, insufficient digital literacy skills hinder students' ability to critically evaluate online sources for credibility, relevance and authority, exacerbating the risk of misinformation and academic dishonesty (Garbe & Soukup, 2025). Hence, intervention such as information literacy instruction to improve students' computer self-efficacy and behavioural skills is

indispensable in overcoming impediments against the use of OIRs by LIS students.

Empirical Studies

Liu and Ma (2017) investigated the impact of computer self-efficacy on students' satisfaction and performance in online learning environments. Findings revealed that higher levels of computer self-efficacy were associated with greater satisfaction with the online learning experience and improved academic outcomes, highlighting the mediating role of perceived usefulness in this relationship.

Akpojotor (2016) investigated the awareness and use of OIRs among postgraduate students of library and information science in Southern Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The questionnaire tagged: 'Awareness and Usage of Electronic Information Resources by Postgraduate Students of Library and Information Science Questionnaire' (AUEIRPSLISQ) was used as instrument for data collection. The results obtained revealed that postgraduate students of library and information science were quite aware and highly used electronic information resources. The study also reported that postgraduate LIS students were skilled in the use of OIRs. Based on the findings, the study concluded that OIRs are essential tools for

empowering postgraduate students of library and information science in Southern Nigeria. Omotayo and Haliru (2020) in their study investigated task-technology fit of digital libraries in three Nigerian Universities and identified factors influencing use of digital library by the students. Survey design guided the study and a questionnaire was used to collect data from 402 students. The study found a high use of digital library among the students. Computer self-efficacy, another variable in the study has moderate positive correlation and significant relationship with use of digital library by the University students. Overall, the results demonstrated that the students' skill and competence at using technology and the Internet influenced their use of digital library. Hence, students need to be encouraged to acquire computing skills in order to be relevant in modern day technology-driven world.

Saunders et al. (2015) used a survey on information behaviours to address a gap in the literature by examining how LIS students in 18 countries search for, evaluate, and use information in various contexts, and on whom they rely for help, demonstrating LIS students' information literacy skills within an international context. Students were asked about the perceived level of difficulty for 13

tasks related to starting a course assignment and searching for resources for that assignment. According to the responses, LIS students generally found the pre-research work to be more difficult than the tasks related to finding and evaluating resources. LIS students relied heavily on search engines, and express some concern about their ability to evaluate Web sources. They also reported concern with determining what constitutes plagiarism and knowing when to cite sources. While these behaviours and attitudes are understandable, they raise some concerns as to whether LIS students, are moving beyond the general population in their location, search, evaluate and use resources and build up information literacy skills necessary to add value to their information seeking and searching.

Hebert (2018) in a cross-sectional, descriptive study seeks to address a gap in knowledge of both Information Literacy (IL), computer self-efficacy and IL skills of students entering Louisiana State University's Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) programme. An online survey testing both IL computer self-efficacy and skills was administered through Qualtrics and was distributed to two cohorts of incoming students. the first cohort entered

the MLIS programme in fall 2017, and the second entered in spring 2018.

The students in the spring 2018 cohort were more confident; the mean score for each area was above 4.0, indicating most students felt like they had adequate skills in all six areas. Although the majority of students in both cohorts felt like their skills were adequate, 72% were unable to identify the best source to locate a brief history and summary of a topic, while 59% were unable to select the best way to locate a journal article using the library's catalogue. Therefore, use of OIRs is aided by the computer self-efficacy and behavioural skills of the students. It is integral to the academic and professional endeavours of LIS students, enabling access to a vast array of scholarly content and research tools.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. Three universities, made up of one federal university, one state university and one private university all in Kwara State, were selected for the study. The selected universities are: University of Ilorin, Kwara State University and Al-Hikma university, respectively. All the 523 final year LIS students of the three universities selected, 87 from University of Ilorin, 430 from Kwara

State University and 6 from Al-Hikma University, constituted the study population. Using a Random Number Generator from within the range of 100 to 120 while allowing for duplicate numbers, a sample size of 108 was drawn. Questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument. Its internal consistency strength was tested and it yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.71, indicating an acceptable level of reliability. One hundred and eight structured and validated

copies of questionnaire were administered, but only 88 were returned, giving the return rate of 81.5%. The returned copies of the questionnaire were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 24). Frequency distribution, percentage and arithmetic mean were used to present data.

Results of the Study

A total of 108 copies of the questionnaire were administered to students across the three selected universities in Kwara State and 88 (81.5%) were returned and used for the analysis.

Demographics of the respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents by Demographics

Age	Frequency	Percentage%
18-23	70	79.6
24-29	17	19.3
30-35	1	1.2
Above 35	-	-
Total	88	100
Gender	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	36	40.9
Female	52	59.1
Total	88	100

Table 1 shows that out of the 88 respondents, a majority 70(79.6%) were within 18- 23 age bracket, while only 1(1.2%) was within 30-35 age bracket. This implies that majority of the respondents were within the age bracket of 18- 23 years. The table also showed that out of the 88 respondents, more than average 52(59.1%) were female, while the remaining 36(40.9%) were male. This suggests that more female participated in the study.

Analysis of Research Questions

RQ 1: What is the level of computer Self-efficacy among LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara State?

Students were asked to indicate their level of computer self-efficacy. The result is presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Level of Computer Self-efficacy among LIS Students in the selected universities in Kwara State

Computer Self-efficacy level	VH Freq(%)	H Freq(%)	M Freq(%)	L Freq(%)	VL Freq(%)	Mean	Std. Dev
How would you rate your ability to use word processing software?	26(29.5)	52(59.1)	8(9.1)	2(2.3)	-	2.0466	0.35571
How would you rate your ability to use spreadsheet software?	5(5.7)	6(6.8)	29(32.9)	41(46.6)	7(8.0)	1.7434	0.47047
How will you rate your ability to troubleshoot basic computer problems?	6(6.8)	10(11.4)	47(53.4)	22(25.0)	3(3.4)	1.8934	0.55048
How would you rate your ability to navigate and use online library databases and resources?	5(5.7)	55(62.5)	19(21.6)	9(10.2)	-	2.2734	0.83406
How would you rate your ability to learn and use new software	2(2.3)	13(14.8)	30(34.1)	39(44.3)	4(4.5)	1.5534	0.46126

introduced by the library?

N = 6 Criterion mean = 2.5 Weighted mean $12.20 \div 6 = 2.03$ 12.198

(Key: VH= Very High; H=High; M=Moderate; L= Low; VL= Very Low)

From Table 2, it was clearly shown that all the items relating to the level of computer Self-efficacy fell below the criterion mean of 2.5, with level of ability to learn and use new software application introduced by library as lowest ($\bar{x} = 1.55$).

RQ2: What behavioural skills do LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara State exhibit when accessing OIRs?

Students were asked to indicate the kind of behavioural skills they exhibit when accessing the OIRs. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Behavioural Skills exhibited LIS Students in the selected universities in Kwara State

Behavioural Skills Exhibited	SA	A	D	SD
	Frequency/ %	Frequency/ %	Frequency/ %	Frequency/ %
I effectively manage my time when searching for OIRs of library.	10(11.4)	77(87.5)	1(1.1)	-
I am proactive in seeking help when I encounter difficulties with my searching.	62(70.5)	21(23.8)	5(5.6)	-
I regularly use online resources to enhance my learning and research skills.	59(67.0)	19(21.6)	8(9.1)	2(2.3)
I participate actively in group projects and discussion.	12(13.6)	72(81.8)	2(2.3)	2(2.3)

I stay updated with the latest developments and trends in LIS. 10(11.4) 30(34.1) 42(47.7) 6(6.8)

(Key: SA= Strongly Agree; A=Agree; S= Disagree; SD= Strongly Disagree)

Table 3 shows that majority of the respondents 62(70.5%) strongly agreed that they proactively sought help when they encountered difficulties with searching, while the least 10(11.4) strongly agreed they effectively managed their time when searching for OIRs of library and stayed updated with the latest developments and trends in LIS respectively.

RQ 3: What is the extent to which LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara State use OIRs for academic and professional purposes?

The result on the extent of use of OIRs is presented in the Table 4.

Table 4: Extent of use of OIRs among LIS Students in the selected universities in Kwara State

Extent of the Use of OIRs	GE	ME	LE	VLE	NAA
	freq%	freq%	freq%	freq%	freq%
To what extent do you use online databases for your academic research?	70(79.5)	18(20.5)	-	-	-
To what extent do you rely on online journals to find relevant academic articles?	62(70.5)	26(29.5)	-	-	-
To what extent do you use online resources provided by your library?	6(6.8)	10(11.4)	26(29.5)	42(47.7)	-
To what extent do you use online search engines to find scholarly information?	81(92.0)	9(8.2)	-	-	-

To what extent do you access online e-books and other digital resources for your coursework?	77(87.5)	11(20.4)	-	-	-
To what extent do you use online tutorials and guides to improve your research skills?	42(47.7)	26(29.5)	10(11.4)	10(11.4)	-

(Key- GE=Great Extent; ME= Moderate Extent; LE= Low Extent; VLE= Very Low Extent; NAA= Not at All

Table 4 reveals that majority of the respondents 81(92.0) indicated they used online search engines to find scholarly information at great extent, followed by 77(87.5) respondents who revealed they accessed online e-books and other digital resources for coursework. In contrast, the majority 42(47.7) expressed that they used online resources provided by their libraries very less often.

RQ 4: What attitudinal disposition do LIS students in the selected universities in Kwara State exhibit when using OIRs?

The results on the attitudinal disposition when using OIRs by LIS students are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Attitudinal Disposition when using OIRs among LIS Students in the selected universities in Kwara State

Attitudes	SA	A	D	SD
	Frequency/%	Frequency/%	Frequency/%	Frequency/%
I find it difficult to access some online databases due to subscription restriction.	62(70.5)	21(23.9)	5(5.7)	-
I struggle to identify credible and reliable sources of online information.	10(11.4)	30(34.1)	42(47.7)	6(6.8)

I often face technical issues when accessing online resources.	12(13.6)	72(81.8)	2(2.3)	2(2.3)
I find it challenging to effectively use advanced search features of online library databases.	59(67.0)	19(21.6)	8(9.1)	2(2.3)
I have limited knowledge of the online resources available through my library.	17(17.0)	13(13.0)	65(65.0)	5(5.0)
I feel that I need more training to use OIRs effectively.	7(8.0)	81(92.0)	-	-
I often think that information I need is not available in online library resources.	1(1.1)	25(51.1)	50(56.8)	12(13.6)

(Key: SA= Strongly Agree; A=Agree; S= Disagree; SD= Strongly Disagree)

The result in Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents 81(92.0) expressed the opinion that they felt they needed more training to use OIRs effectively. This is closely followed by 72(81.8) respondents who indicated they often faced technical issues when accessing online resources. However, majority of respondents 62(70.5) expressed opinion that they found it difficult to access some online databases, followed by 59(67.0) who found it challenging to effectively use advanced search features in online databases.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study indicated a low level of computer self-efficacy among the LIS students, with level of ability to learn and use new software application introduced by library as the lowest. Many respondents reported low level of confidence in their computer skills, which could significantly impact their productivity and learning outcomes. Findings of the study revealed that

respondents often sought help when they encountered difficulties with searching and could not effectively managed their time when searching for OIRs of library. This is supported by Hebert (2018) in a cross-sectional, descriptive study that sought to address a gap in knowledge of both information literacy self-efficacy and skills of students entering Louisiana State University's Master of Library and

Information Science (MLIS) programme. Although the majority of students felt like their skills were adequate, 72% were unable to identify the best source to locate a brief history and summary of a topic, while 59% were unable to select the best way to locate a journal article using the library's catalogue.

Findings of the study also showed a high extent of use of search engines by LIS students to find scholarly information. This reliance on search engines seems to suggest that LIS students less frequently used library databases for their OIRs to stay informed and up-to-date. This deduction is reinforced by further finding which showed that respondents used online resources provided by their libraries very less often. This is similar to the findings of Saunders et al. (2015) who found that LIS students relied heavily on search engines, and expressed concern about their ability to evaluate Web sources.

Findings further showed that respondents needed more training to use OIRs effectively as they often faced technical issues when accessing online resources. Most respondents also faced difficulty due to the nature of the advanced search features of online library databases. Omotayo and Haliru, (2020) in their study demonstrated

that the students' skill and competence in using technology and the Internet influenced their use of library resources. Hence, students need to be encouraged to acquire computing skills in order to be relevant in modern day technology-driven world.

Conclusion

There is an indication of a low level of computer self-efficacy among the LIS students, with level of ability to learn and use new software application introduced by library being the lowest. Low level of confidence in computer skills has led students to often seek help when they encountered difficulties when searching OIRs of library. This explains the high extent of use of search engines by LIS students to find scholarly information. This reliance on search engines also seemed to explain why students used online resources provided by their libraries very less often.

However, students' poor disposition towards the use of OIRs of library is partly attributable to the challenges posed by complex nature of the advanced search features of the online library databases. Therefore, enhancing digital literacy education through training will empower the students to adeptly navigate digital platforms, critically evaluate information sources, and

more efficiently manage information for their academic and professional overload. This is to ensure that students can development in today's digital era. harness the full potentials of online resources

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made, aiming to enhance computer self-efficacy and behavioural skills of the LIS students:

1. The University management should hold regular training sessions, integrate digital literacy courses into the curriculum to enhance computer self-efficacy of students in order to maximally explore the under used OIRs.
2. Moral and ethical standards should be upheld by the library management to improve students' behavioural skills in retrieving and using of OIRs.
3. Adequate and relevant online resources, subscription to relevant databases and good Internet services should be put in place by the parent institutions to sustain the interest of the students in exploring OIRs.
4. The parent institutions should ensure provision of enough ICT gadgets, regular training of all information professionals and increased funding for their libraries to address technical and financial issues provoking the optimal use of OIRs.

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